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Fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens

Technical Memorandum To Support Deliverable 5.7
[Using 0.16T CTS Data To Predict T_0 And Bounds To Toughness Data
From Larger Specimens]

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¹ **Nature:** R -Document, report; DEM -Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; DEC -Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER; ETHICS -Ethics requirement; ORDP -Open Research Data Pilot; DATA -data sets, microdata, etc.

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Glossary

ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
Campaign	Used in this report to refer to a program outside FRACTESUS in which a set of K_{Jc} versus T data or T_0 measurements were acquired using specimens larger than 0.16T
CRP	Coordinated Research Program
CTS	Compact Tension Specimen
DBTT	Ductile to Brittle Transition Temperature
IAEA	International Atomic Energy Agency
K_{Jc}	Toughness measurement
$K_{Jc,0.16T}$ $K_{Jc,1T}$	K_{Jc} measurement acquired using a 0.16T or 1T specimen (respectively)
Large- T_0	Used in this report to describe a measurement of T_0 derived from a set of specimens larger than 0.16T (i.e. with a crack front longer than 4mm)
Miniature	Used in this report to refer to a 0.16T compact tension specimen
Mini- T_0	Used in this report to describe a measurement of T_0 derived from a set of 0.16T compact tension specimens
pcCv	Pre-cracked Charpy-shaped specimen
SENB	Single edge-notched bend specimen
Subset	Used in this report to refer to a set of K_{Jc} versus T data or T_0 measurements acquired in a single laboratory in the FRACTESUS program (using 0.16T CTSs)
t	The thickness of a material, such that 0.25t or 0.5t etc. refer to the location through the thickness
T	Temperature
1T	Unit thickness (crack front length) of a Compact Tension Sample (1", 25mm) such that e.g. 0.16T refers to a CTS with a crack front length of 4mm
T_0	The temperature at which the median toughness is $100\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ when data are analysed according to the Master curve and a dataset is homogeneous
$T_{0\text{scrn}}$	The screening temperature used to determine whether a K_{Jc} versus temperature dataset is homogeneous within the Master curve analysis. Used in place of T_0 when a dataset is inhomogeneous, but there are too few measurements (<20) for a multimodal analysis to be performed.
T_{max}	The temperature used to replace T_0 when a steel is inhomogeneous, but the dataset contains ≤ 9 measurements.
T_m	The temperature at which the median toughness is $100\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ in an inhomogeneous dataset analysed according to the multimodal Master curve method
WOL	Wedge Opening Load Specimen
σ	Standard deviation
$\sigma_{\text{material variability}}$	Contribution to variability in T_0 caused by place-to-place variations in material properties (inhomogeneities)
μ_N	Mean of normal distribution fitted to T_0 measurements obtained in different subsets / campaigns

σ_N	Standard deviation of normal distribution fitted to T_0 measurements obtained in different subsets / campaigns
σ_{T0}	Contribution to standard deviation on T_0 due to the number and distribution of toughness measurements in the dataset
σ_{Tm}	Contribution to standard deviation on T_m due to the number and distribution of toughness measurements in the inhomogeneous dataset

1 Introduction

There is a continuing trend, especially within the nuclear industry, to acquire increasing amounts of information from ever-smaller amounts of test material. This is economic with scarce material (e.g. material from surveillance or test irradiations) and allows testing of product forms and components of geometries from which standard, large specimens cannot be extracted. Despite many programs intended to show that small specimens can be used to derive valid measurements of toughness and the ductile-to-brittle transition temperature (DBTT), some materials scientists and engineers and in particular, operators of nuclear power plant and Regulators retain concerns about the transferability of data derived from small specimens.

The FRACTESUS Horizon 2020 project combines European and International efforts aiming to establish a more secure foundation for fracture toughness measurement using small specimens (assuming that this proves possible). The project further aims to use this foundation to develop and demonstrate the procedures necessary to acquire comparable information from 4mm thick and full-sized specimens, then to support appropriate changes to current codes and standards to incorporate the best practices identified within FRACTESUS. Ultimately, the FRACTESUS consortium hopes to be able to address the various national regulatory authority concerns about data derived from small specimens and make the use of such data more widely acceptable in safety assessments.

As part of the FRACTESUS project, six different reactor pressure vessel steels were identified, covering a range of product forms, compositions and transition temperatures [1]. All of these steels had been tested previously in the form of large specimens, often in more than one specimen geometry. Sections or specimens of these steels were acquired by FRACTESUS and manufactured into 4mm thick (0.16T, where 1T indicates a thickness of 1"=25.4mm) miniature compact tension specimens (CTSs). Deliverable 3.3 of the project [2] describes the fracture toughness data acquired by different laboratories and compares the data with measurements acquired on larger specimens for six different reactor pressure vessel steels [1].

Valid toughness measurements can be acquired from miniature, 0.16T CTSs only at low toughness levels. Extrapolating from these levels to the levels of interest for structural integrity assessments, or to define a DBTT, requires an agreed temperature-dependence for the toughness data. This is taken to be Wallin's Master curve [3]. All the FRACTESUS data were analysed on the assumption that the temperature-dependence and scatter in the data reflect the properties of the Master curve as outlined in the ASTM E1921-21 Standard Test Method [4]. This standard defines the DBTT as the Master curve reference temperature, T_0 , and defines the expected bounds associated with different percentages of the data. It also defines an uncertainty in the estimate of T_0 based on the number and distribution of the toughness measurements in a dataset (σ_{T_0}), and provides a method whereby a more conservative estimate of the lower bounds can be made, taking into account this uncertainty (the margin-adjusted bounds). Finally, E1921, contains a procedure for assessing whether the distribution of toughness measurements indicates that the material tested is homogeneous and provides alternative ways of describing the bounds if the data set is inhomogeneous.

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This memo describes investigations carried out at NNL comparing data acquired from large and miniature specimens of the FRACTESUS steels in terms of the ASTM E1921-21 parameters. It focusses in most detail on data from two of the FRACTESUS steels which showed the least direct relation between data from 0.16T and larger specimens. The aim is to use the data from these steels to identify when simple methods of using toughness data from miniature specimens will predict material properties adequately, and when additional care will be required. These observations can then be used to develop a general method of utilising toughness data from miniature specimens, which can be applied to any previously-uncharacterised RPV steel.

The Master curve methodology can be used to identify a good description of the mean dependence of K_{Jc} on temperature for a steel, or to identify the bounds to the distribution of K_{Jc} values about the mean. Both are useful in structural integrity assessments. This report therefore considers both (i) the relation between DBTT measurements measured in 0.16T and larger specimens and (ii) the relation between bounds predicted by 0.16T data and the distribution of K_{Jc} measurements made in larger specimens. Section 2 and 3 make comparisons between the basic T_0 measurements derived from large and small specimens, utilising T_0 values derived from the overall FRACTESUS $K_{Jc, 0.16T}$ dataset or from sub-sets of the FRACTESUS data, as acquired in the laboratories of the individual partners. The characteristics of these measurements indicate that it is important to take into account material inhomogeneity. Section 4 therefore describes the methods recommended in ASTM E1921-21 [4] for treating datasets exhibiting inhomogeneity and applies these methods. It then compares the inhomogeneity-corrected T_0 values derived from small and large specimen. Section 5 compares inhomogeneity-corrected bounds derived from the analysis of 0.16T K_{Jc} data with sets of K_{Jc} data acquired from larger specimens. Section 6 discusses the outcomes of these comparisons while Section 7 summarises the results and conclusions.

2 Overall Comparisons – DBTT

Figure 1-Figure 3 use different ways to present comparisons between the initial T_0 values (i.e. T_0 according to paragraph 10.5 of ASTM E1921-21, prior to the inhomogeneity assessment, also described as T_{0step1} within the inhomogeneity assessment) measured in miniature (0.16T) CTSs and larger specimens³. The larger specimen datasets are those identified for comparison in [1]. The individual laboratory campaigns summarised in [1] may have utilised pre-cracked Charpy-sized single edge-notched bend specimens (pcCv, 0.4T SENB), 0.5T – 8T compact tension specimens (CTSs) or wedge opening loading (WOL) specimens. The T_0 values derived from pcCv specimens are increased by $8\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ in these Figures to match the values from similarly-sized CTS samples.

In Figure 1, the y-axis is the average of the T_0 values measured in different campaigns using large specimens [1], with the associated error bar indicating the standard deviation among these T_0 values. The x-axis is the T_0 value derived from the overall FRACTESUS dataset [2], and the error bar gives the associated $1\sigma_{T_0}$ (equation 29, paragraph 10.9 in ASTM E1921-21) calculated using TOTEM software. In five of the six materials selected (all steels other than 73W), the points are within 1-2 error bars of the

³ The data from ANP-5 exclude those from the sample which was found to have been untempered [2].

one-to-one line, indicating that, given sufficient data, the miniature and larger specimens give consistent estimates of T_0 . For one of the six selected steels (73W, with the second-lowest T_0 values), the data from large and miniature samples fall further from the one-to-one line. The FRACTESUS steels were selected to exhibit a wide range of material properties. It is not immediately obvious which of these (or other) properties cause the behaviour of 73W to differ from that of the other steels, but it is important to note that one in six is not a trivial fraction. The possible causes of 73W's deviation from the one-to-one relation will be investigated further in a later section.

Figure 1: Comparison between initial T_0 values from miniature and larger specimens of different RPV steels used in the FRACTESUS program.

More detail is given in Figure 2 and Figure 3. In Figure 2, the average and standard deviation of the T_0 values derived in different campaigns using large specimens of the FRACTESUS RPV steels (as in Figure 1) are compared with the $T_0 \pm \sigma_{T_0}$ values derived from individual laboratories' measurements on miniature CTSs in the FRACTESUS program⁴. In Figure 3, $T_0 \pm \sigma_{T_0}$ from the combined FRACTESUS datasets are compared with the individual $T_0 \pm \sigma_{T_0}$ values from different campaigns using larger specimens, as described in Table 4 of [1].

⁴ For the remainder of this report, the results from an individual laboratory within the FRACTESUS project will be referred to as a "subset" of the FRACTESUS data. The results from large specimens from different sources in the literature will be referred to as results from different "campaigns".

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Figure 2: Comparison between averages of T_0 measured in large samples and individual values of T_0 measured by different groups using miniature samples.

Figure 3: Comparison between values of T_0 measured using entire FRACTESUS datasets from miniature CTSs of different RPV steels and individual values of T_0 measured by different groups using larger specimens.

It is noteworthy that both the large- and miniature-specimen data in *Figure 2* and *Figure 3* show a range of T_0 estimates. A larger proportion of the T_0 values from different campaigns using large specimens do not overlap at the $2\sigma_{T_0}$ level than would be expected from a normal distribution characterized by σ_{T_0} : the same is true for the T_0 values from different subsets of miniature specimens. In consequence, when comparing a T_0 value from a single large specimen campaign with that from a single miniature specimen subset it is likely that the two will differ by more than $\pm 2\sigma_{T_0}$, even in steels for which the average values (*Figure 1*) are consistent. This may cause results from mini-CTSs to appear inappropriately conservative or non-conservative with respect to large specimen data.

The subset-to-subset variability in T_0 from the miniature samples appears larger than the campaign-to-campaign variability in T_0 from the larger samples, but these representations do not show whether this is caused by a specimen size effect or is simply due to the larger number of miniature specimen data sets in this comparison. Further investigation is required to clarify this point.

The main questions arising from the basic comparisons shown in this Section are:

- Why is the campaign-to-campaign or subset-to-subset variability in T_0 so much larger than suggested by σ_{T_0} ?
- Why is the behaviour of 73W unlike that of the other RPV steels?

The next Section investigates the distributions of the T_0 values derived from different subsets of the FRACTESUS data and different campaigns in the literature to help clarify these questions.

3 Behaviour of Different Steels - DBTT

Figure 4 represents the data in more detail, comparing the individual T_0 values from each subset of the FRACTESUS data from each material. The T_0 values for the 0.16T CTS data sets (“mini- T_0 ”) are the initial values calculated in the ASTM procedure ($T_{0\text{step1}}$ in the terminology of paragraph 10.6 of ASTM E1921-21) and the error bars are $\pm 1\sigma_{T_0}$.

The cumulative probabilities are determined by ordering the T_0 values from a given steel in order of increasing temperature and assigning each a rank, r . The probability is then calculated as

$$\text{Cumulative Probability} = \frac{r - 0.3}{N + 0.4}$$

where N is the number of T_0 values in the distribution (the number of data subsets).

A normal distribution is fitted to the cumulative probability of each set of mini- T_0 values (defined by a mean, μ_N , and a standard deviation σ_N). For convenience, the T_0 values reported in the literature for larger specimens (“large- T_0 ” $\pm 1\sigma_{T_0}$) are plotted at a cumulative probability of 0.5. (No adjustment is made for pcCv versus CTS geometries in these plots.)

As expected from the interpretations of *Figure 1-Figure 3*, *Figure 4* shows there is always a range in the mini- T_0 values determined by different laboratories, and individual measurements frequently fail to

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overlap at the $2\sigma_{T_0}$ level. This would be expected for any distribution of measurements, but the proportion shown in Table 1 is much higher than would be expected from normal distributions characterized by T_0 and σ_{T_0} . Investigation of *Figure 4* also shows that the large- T_0 values also fail to overlap at the $2\sigma_{T_0}$ level in a disproportionately large number of cases. σ_{T_0} is intended to show the uncertainty of T_0 based on the number and distribution of the datapoints and the experimental uncertainty. This suggests that the range in mini- T_0 values (and that in large- T_0 values) is affected by place-to-place variability in the material i.e. inhomogeneity.

Figure 4: Cumulative probability distributions of mini- T_0 measurements from different FRACTESUS laboratories compared with individual large- T_0 measurements from the literature.

Table 1. Separation of T_0 values derived from different sub-sets of the FRACTESUS measurements.

Material	Number of data sub-sets	Number of possible pair-wise combinations	Number of pairs that do not overlap at $2\sigma_{T_0}$
15Kh2MFAA	6	15	8
73W	5	10	8
JRQ	6	15	3
A508 Class 3	5	10	5
ANP-5	5	10	4
A533B LUS	3	3	0

The fitted normal distributions in *Figure 4* are characterized by a mean (μ_N) and a standard deviation (σ_N). If the standard deviations (σ_N) of the cumulative probability distributions indicate the total variability, then comparing this with σ_{T_0} allows the magnitude of the place-to-place variability to be estimated:

$$\sigma_N^2 = \sigma_{T_0}^2 + \sigma_{\text{material variability}}^2$$

Table 2: Contribution of material variability to uncertainty in T_0 .

Material	Average value of σ_{T_0} derived from FRACTESUS subsets ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	σ_N ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	$\sigma_{\text{material variability}}$ ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
15Kh2MFAA	6.35	12.99	11.33
73W	7.36	26.18	25.12
A533B-JRQ	6.47	8.07	4.83
A508 Cl3	7.44	15.67	13.79
ANP-5	6.62	13.73	12.03
A533B-LUS	7.1	5.37	<0

The magnitude of the place-to-place variability thereby appears to be smallest for A533B-JRQ and A533B-LUS, at $<5^{\circ}\text{C}$, and greatest for 73W, at $\sim 25^{\circ}\text{C}$, with the remaining welds (ANP-5) and base metals (15Kh2MFAA and A508 Cl 3) exhibiting material variability of 10-15 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. There is no obvious correlation between the widths of the distributions and the fraction of the subsets identified as inhomogeneous.

Combining these observations in different ways gives average values of $\sigma_{\text{material variability}}$ of 19 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the FRACTESUS welds, 7 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the base metals and 11 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ overall. *Figure 5* reproduces *Figure 3* using error bars of $\sqrt{\sigma_{T_0}^2 + 11^{\circ}\text{C}}$. The relation of the data to the one-to-one line is now generally more convincing, although the 73W data are still within $2\sigma_{\text{total}}$ of the one-to-one line only if $\sigma_{\text{material variability}}=19^{\circ}\text{C}$ or 26 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ is used rather than the average value of 11 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The analysis in this section thus indicates that the subset-to-subset variability in the 0.16T CTS-derived T_0 values is sufficient to account for apparent differences

between mini- T_0 and large- T_0 . Material inhomogeneity must, therefore, be taken into account when comparing T_0 values from different sources.

Figure 5: Comparison between values of T_0 measured using entire FRACTESUS datasets from miniature CTSs of different RPV steels and individual values of T_0 measured by different groups using larger specimens.

$$\text{Error bars} = \sigma_N^2 = \sigma_{T_0}^2 + \sigma_{\text{material variability}}^2, \text{ where } \sigma_{\text{material variability}} = 11^\circ\text{C}.$$

Considering the relation between individual mini- T_0 and large- T_0 values further, *Figure 4* shows that, in most cases, the large- T_0 values fall within the 10th - 90th percentile range of the mini- T_0 distribution. The exception is the large- T_0 derived for JRQ using the 0.5T CTSs. Since deviations from the average behaviour are providing information on the ways in which inhomogeneity affects toughness characteristics, this case, as well as that of 73W, are considered further below.

3.1 More Detailed Investigation of 73W

The large- T_0 values reported in [1] and used for comparisons in *Figure 4* came from the analysis of CTS data (1T-8T) acquired during the 5th Heavy Section Steel Irradiation Program [5]. The toughness measurements reported in [5] have been regrouped here according to (a) test temperature and (b) specimen size then reanalysed with TOTEM to provide a larger population of large- T_0 measurements with which the mini- T_0 measurements can be compared. The comparison is shown in *Figure 6*. The

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cumulative probability distributions (*Figure 6a*) show that the distributions of T_0 values from 0.16T and 1T-8T CTSs are not similar. The mini- T_0 values are distributed to much lower temperatures than the larger-specimen values, and are more widely spread. (Note the highest mini- T_0 datum was invalid due to the small number of K_{Ic} measurements.) The overlap between the distributions of mini- T_0 and large- T_0 from 73W is minimal.

Since miniature CTSs are tested at lower average temperatures than larger specimens to avoid large scale yielding, the effects of average test temperature are shown in *Figure 6b*. While the mini- T_0 estimates are very strongly dependent upon the average test temperature, the large- T_0 values are barely test-temperature dependent, so test temperature alone does not explain the difference in behaviour. *Figure 6c* shows that the difference between mini- T_0 and large- T_0 is also not a continuous effect of specimen size. These results are consistent with those of Chaouadi [6], who also found no temperature-dependence of T_0 when looking at the HSSI CTS data, or at pcCv samples of 73W, and obtained a tight range in T_0 when examining subsets of the CTS data (1σ approximately 6°C, based on the appearance of *Figure 7* of [6]).

Figure 6: Comparison between mini- T_0 and large- T_0 in 73W. (a) Cumulative probability distributions (b) Effect of average test temperature (c) Effect of specimen size.

This leaves the scale of material inhomogeneity as a possible cause of the difference between miniature and larger-specimen data. The microstructure of 73W is shown in *Figure 7*, annotated with the sizes of the different test specimens [7]. In their analysis of 0.16T CTS data from 73W, Chaouadi and Schuurmans

noted that the scale of the inhomogeneity in the weld was such that a 1T CTS would sample about 15 weld beads while a 0.16T CTS would sample less than one weld bead.

It is generally expected that the $B^{0.25}$ size correction (ASTM E1921-21 paragraph 10.1.4) will account for size effects, as it is intended to account for the effect of crack front length on the likelihood of the plastic zone encompassing a weak link. The distribution in K at a given test temperature is then related to the size / strength distribution of the population of weak links. This, however, is relevant only for a homogeneous distribution of a single population of links. It appears that, in 73W, there is more than one family of weak links, and these are not interspersed homogeneously. Instead, they are separated into different microstructural constituents which are distributed on a size scale such that the more brittle family is always present in the plastic zone of a 1T specimen but may or may not be present within the plastic zone of a miniature specimen.

Figure 7: Comparison between scales of weld beads in 73W and sizes of 0.16T and 1T CTSs [7].

3.2 More Detailed Investigation of JRQ

Investigation of the behaviour of JRQ is aided by the availability of additional T_0 data from the Fifth IAEA Coordinated Research program (CRP5) [8]. Different groups in CRP5 tested pcCv and 1T CTS specimens, and their T_0 measurements are illustrated in Figure 8. Again, values from different laboratories show significant variability, with the laboratory-to-laboratory variability in large- T_0 being very similar to that seen for mini- T_0 in FRACTESUS ($1\sigma_N=9^\circ\text{C}$ for the pcCv dataset and 16°C for the 1T CTS set.). The large- T_0 of -42.2°C reported for the 0.5T CTS, which appeared unexpectedly high in Figure 4 is now seen to be consistent with either the 95th percentile of the 0.16T range or lower percentiles in the 1T distribution.

Figure 8: Distributions of large- T_0 values measured by different participants in the IAEA CRP5 round robin on JRQ indicating specimen type (pcCv or 1T CTS) and location through thickness (t) of Block 6 from which specimens were cut. Comparison with mini- T_0 values measured by FRACTESUS partners.

In IAEA TECDOC 1435 [8], the range in T_0 values was ascribed to the heterogeneous microstructure of JRQ. The microstructure is mainly bainitic with both lower bainite and martensite near the surface and upper bainite and reticularly arranged martensite in the centre, as illustrated in Figure 9. (There was no micron marker associated with Figure 9b but it is plausible that the magnification is the same as in Figure 9a.)

Figure 9: Optical micrographs showing the variability in the microstructure of JRQ plate (a) Block 5 (b) Block 6 [8].

The pcCv data from $\frac{1}{4}t + \frac{3}{4}t$ and from $\frac{1}{2}t$ (where t =thickness position through the plate from which the specimens were cut) showed the same cumulative probability distribution, so are plotted as a single distribution in Figure 8 but, although there are clear overlaps among all the distributions, the distributions of T_0 from the 0.16T and 1T specimens differ from that from pcCv specimens. The most significant difference is between the large- T_0 values based on pcCv data and the large- T_0 values based on 1T CTS data in the CRP5 data. The separation between the two distributions is $\sim 20^\circ\text{C}$ at a cumulative probability of 0.5. This is larger than the expected difference based on geometry alone ($\sim 8 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$). It is

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not related to any differences in the depths ($\frac{1}{4}$, $\frac{1}{2}$ or $\frac{3}{4}$ thickness) from which the specimens were cut. The difference between the distributions of large- T_0 from the CRP5 pcCv data and mini- T_0 from FRACTESUS (8°C) is, however, consistent with the general literature. This suggests that there is a specimen size effect appearing, not between 0.16T and 0.4T, but between 0.4T and 1T. As with 73W, the JRQ data appear to be affected by the scale of the material inhomogeneity. In JRQ, plastic zones in the pcCv and 0.16T CTSs may fail to encompass the more brittle microstructural constituent while the larger plastic zones in the 1T CTSs more regularly include it. Looking at the scale of the microstructures in *Figure 9*, both the 0.16T and the 1T crack fronts appear long enough to sample dark and light regions of the microstructure. The constituent which shifts and broadens the distribution of T_0 values derived from 1T JRQ data thus appears to be associated with inhomogeneity on a larger scale than the features seen in the microstructural examination.

Given the overlap in the distributions from the pcCv, 0.16T and 1T measurements, it appears likely that the difference in strength between the two families of weak links in JRQ is smaller than in 73W.

Overall, this preliminary assessment of the average characteristics of the data shows that:

- (1) allowing for a contribution to the uncertainty on T_0 from material inhomogeneity renders the one-to-one correlation between average large- T_0 and mini- T_0 more convincing for most steels (comparing *Figure 3* with *Figure 5*),
- (2) both base and weld metals can be microstructurally inhomogeneous on a scale relevant to toughness samples (*Figure 7* and *Figure 9*),
- (3) assuming that a sample can contain more than one population of weak links, and that the two populations need not be homogeneously interspersed, can explain the different behaviours of 73W, JRQ and the other RPV steels in the FRACTESUS program (*Figure 6a* and *Figure 8*),

This suggests it is worth considering the treatment of inhomogeneity in ASTM E1921, and its application to the relation between miniature specimen measurements and those from larger specimens. This is done in the next section.

4 Inhomogeneity

4.1 Screening for Inhomogeneity

ASTM E1921-21 [4] contains procedures for identifying whether a dataset is inhomogeneous i.e. whether the distribution of toughness measurements is such that it is unlikely that the data are describable using a single Master curve. The Standard considers that this may arise from microstructural inhomogeneity, suggesting, “For example, multipass weldments can create heat-affected and brittle zones with localized properties that are quite different from either the bulk or weld materials. Thick-section steels also often exhibit some variation in properties near the surfaces” [4]. As illustrated by JRQ, RPV base metals may also exhibit an overall mixed microstructure in addition to near-surface effects, containing both ferrite and bainite, upper and lower bainite or bainite and martensite. Material inhomogeneity is, thus, a very likely cause of “inhomogeneity” in a toughness data set. The procedure would, however, also ascribe

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inhomogeneity to the dataset if the underlying material were homogeneous but with toughness that did not follow the Master curve. The E1921 formalism thus allows for a consistent analysis of steel toughness behaviour regardless of the absolute applicability of the Master curve⁵.

Since the assessment requires that the difference between the observed data distribution and the ideal be statistically significant, “the confidence that the screening criterion has correctly identified the material as macroscopically inhomogeneous increases as the number of data points in the data set increases, as the differences in the fracture toughness between lower and higher-toughness material constituents contained within the data set increases, and as the relative amounts of these lower and higher-toughness constituents become more equivalent. However, it is not possible to have reasonable confidence in this screening criterion unless the data set contains at least 20 K_{Jc} values” [4]. In most cases, datasets do not contain more than 20 measurements, so identification of a dataset as inhomogeneous (or a failure to identify inhomogeneity) must be accepted with caution.

The first stage in the homogeneity assessment involves determining the best fit T_0 (T_{0step1}) using a least-squares best fit to the data, modified to take account of the invalid data in the dataset (E1921-21 Sections 10-10.5). The next stage (E1921-21 Section 10.6.2) is based on the SINTAP procedure [9]: the effective toughness of each datum above the median Master curve (based on T_{0step1}) is reduced to the level of the median curve and T_0 is recalculated (leading to T_{0step2}). This procedure is repeated until the difference between T_{0stepn} and $T_{0stepn-1}$ is $<0.5^\circ\text{C}$, whereupon the highest value is taken as T_{0scrn} . The data set can then be defined as homogeneous if (equation 26 in paragraph 10.6.3.1 of ASTM E1921-21):

$$T_{0scrn} - T_{0step1} \leq 1.44 \sqrt{\frac{\beta^2}{r}}$$

where r =total number of uncensored data points in initial calculation of T_{0step1} and β is an uncertainty factor (defined in paragraph 10.9 of [4]).

According to Appendix X5 of E1921-21, if a dataset is inhomogeneous, then a generally conservative estimate of T_0 , T_{0IN} , should be used in place of T_0 . For datasets with more than 9 but fewer than 20 K_{Jc} measurements $T_{0IN} \equiv T_{0scrn}$. If there are fewer than 10 measurements, then a T_{0i} value is calculated for each datum using the assumption that each K_{Jc} is the median for the particular test temperature. The highest value of T_{0i} (T_{0max}) is then compared to T_{0scrn} . If

$$T_{0max} - T_{0scrn} > 8^\circ\text{C}$$

then $T_{0IN} \equiv T_{0max}$; otherwise $T_{0IN} \equiv T_{0scrn}$.

The uncertainty associated with T_{0max} or T_{0scrn} is the same as the value of σ_{T0} calculated for T_0 .

If the dataset contains 20 or more measurements then a multimodal analysis can be performed and $T_{0IN} = T_m$, and σ_{Tm} is used rather than σ_{T0} .

⁵ One of the stakeholder concerns identified within WP1 of FRACTESUS was whether the Mastercurve was truly a characteristic of all RPV steels

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4.2 Screening of FRACTESUS Data

The ASTM screening procedure identifies all the combined 0.16T CTS data sets as inhomogeneous, as illustrated in Table 3. Applying it to the individual subsets of 0.16T measurements, identifies 2/3 of the subsets as inhomogeneous. There is no clear bias for the procedure to define smaller/larger subsets either homogeneous or inhomogeneous. The uncertainty in the outcome of the screening procedure mentioned in E1921-21 does not appear to lead to a default assessment of homogeneity. The assessment of inhomogeneity thus indicates that the differences in T_0 measured in different sub-sets is stochastic, reflecting an uneven distribution of microstructural constituents among the different specimens.

Table 3: Inhomogeneity identified in valid data sets by ASTM E1921 methodology.

Material	Was Inhomogeneity Identified In Dataset?		
	Individual 0.16T*	Combined 0.16T	Larger Samples
15Kh2MFAA	5Y/6 16, 18, 21, 20, 14N, 21	Y	Y (pcCv-28 and 0.5T CTS-15); N (1T CTS-7)
73W	3Y/4* 15, 18, 19N, 14 (7)	Y	N (1T, 2T, 4T CTS-55)
A533B-JRQ	3Y/6 24, 25N, 12N, 16N. 16, 24	Y	N (0.5T-14, 1T CTS and pcCv-10)
A508 Cl.3	3Y/4* 16, 22N, 15, 14, (8)	Y	Y (1T CTS-11); N (0.5T CTS-13)
ANP-5	2Y/4 13N, 14, 16N, 20N, 16	Y	N (pcCv-9 and WOL)
A533B-LUS	2Y/3 12N, 14, 16	Y	Y (0.5T-51 and 1T CTS-54)

* XY/Z indicates that, for X of a total of Z subsets, the question, "Was inhomogeneity identified?" is answered by a "Yes". The following numbers indicate the numbers of K_{Jc} measurements in the individual FRACTESUS subsets. A number followed by "N" shows the subset identified as homogeneous.

In contrast to the 0.16T CTS data subsets, only 1/3 of the larger specimen datasets are defined as inhomogeneous. Most of the larger-specimen datasets have fewer than 20 points but, as with the 0.16T CTS data, there is no evident bias with specimen numbers, so it appears that the imbalance in the results of the screening procedure is identifying a real specimen size effect. i.e. The scales of the material inhomogeneities in the RPV steels examined are such that 0.16T CTSs are likely to sample a single type of microstructure, which may not be the more brittle constituent, while larger specimens will sample a more representative range of microstructures. (Given the range seen in the CRP5 JRQ T_0 measurements in Figure 8, the homogeneity of the K_{Jc} measurements from the pcCv samples of Table 3 is unexpected

but, since only 10 samples are involved in the particular dataset used, this could reflect the uncertainty in the screening procedure.)

4.3 Incorporating Inhomogeneity into DBTT Comparisons

Since the proportion of inhomogeneity differs in the large- and small-specimen datasets, the K_{Ic} measurements alone, even without the microstructural measurements, indicate that extrapolating from small to large specimens will require inhomogeneity to be accounted for correctly. In this context, it is worth noting that, for the three steels in which none of the larger sample datasets showed inhomogeneity, the datapoints in *Figure 1* and *Figure 2* lie above the one-to-one line or, in *Figure 3* are spread with a bias to the left of the one-to-one line i.e. When the scale of the material inhomogeneity is such that only large crack fronts sample both more and less brittle constituents, the range of mini- T_0 values is a non-conservative predictor of the range of large- T_0 values.

The degree to which the $0.16T_0$ estimates are non-conservative can be small (as for ANP-5) large (73W) or intermediate (JRQ) but, if it can be avoided by making the correct allowance for inhomogeneity, this would be well worth including in a procedure.

According to ASTM E1921-21 Appendix X5, if the number of datapoints is between 10 and 20 (as is the case for most of the FRACTESUS subsets), then T_0 is replaced by $T_{0IN}=T_{0scrn}$ and σ_{T_0} remains the same. For larger datasets a full inhomogeneity analysis can be performed and a T_m and σ_{T_m} can be defined. The full inhomogeneity analysis was performed for all the combined FRACTESUS datasets, but only the simpler analysis was performed for the larger samples. T_m is always higher than T_0 , but was more so for the lower values of mini- T_0 than for the higher values. σ_{T_m} is always much larger than σ_{T_0} . T_{0scrn} is also higher than T_0 .

Figure 10 is the equivalent of *Figure 3*, but now using $T_m \pm 1\sigma_{T_m}$ instead of $T_0 \pm 1\sigma_{T_0}$ for the $0.16T$ data and either T_0 or T_{0scrn} , as appropriate, $\pm 1\sigma_{T_0}$ for the larger specimen data. The most significant effect of the changes is that all points are now associated with larger error bars, which cross the one-to-one line. The best fit through the data has also become marginally closer to one-to-one. The steels for which the large specimen data sets did not show inhomogeneity are no longer entirely spread above the one-to-one line.

Figure 10: Comparison between values of $T_m \pm 1\sigma_{Tm}$ measured using entire FRACTESUS datasets from miniature CTSs of different RPV steels and individual values of either $T_0 \pm 1\sigma_{T0}$ or $T_{0scrn} \pm 1\sigma_{T0}$ (depending on homogeneity of dataset) measured by different groups using larger specimens.

Overall, these examinations of the ductile-to-brittle transition temperatures show that, given large enough data sets (>40 points for all the FRACTESUS steels), 0.16T data generally incorporate effects of material inhomogeneity. These effects may not be evident even in subsets with up to 25 points or in data from larger samples. This affects the appropriate analysis of the data.

When T_m is used to describe the 0.16T data, and either T_0 or T_{0scrn} (as appropriate) is used to describe the larger sample data, T_m values derived from K_{Ic} measurements on miniature CTSs are within $1\sigma_{Tm}$ of T_0 (or T_{0scrn}) derived from measurements on larger samples. The average (size-corrected) toughnesses of large and miniature samples are therefore consistent when inhomogeneity is treated according to the recommendations of ASTM E1921-21.

5 Predicting Bounds To Large Specimen Data Using 0.16T CTS Data

The previous sections showed that the average behaviour of miniature specimens was consistent with that of larger specimens once the role of inhomogeneity was recognised and the appropriate description of the DBTT was used, together with an appropriate description of the uncertainty on the DBTT. This section focusses on whether the range in toughness shown by larger specimens can be predicted from

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measurements on miniature CTSs. ASTM E1921-21 identifies different ways of defining a lower bound for both homogeneous and inhomogeneous steels. These methods will be applied to the FRACTESUS and larger specimen data in an effort to identify which methods are most likely to produce reasonable or conservative descriptions of the “5% bound”.

5.1 Definitions of the “Lower Bound”

If the value of T_0 is known with complete certainty, then paragraph 10.8 of ASTM E1921-21 provides an analytical expression for tolerance bounds:

$$K_{Jc(0.xx)} = 20 + \left[\ln \left(\frac{1}{1 - 0.xx} \right) \right]^{0.25} \{11 + 77 \exp[0.019(T - T_0)]\}$$

where 0.xx represents the selected cumulative probability level e.g. for the 5% tolerance bound 0.xx=0.05.

In this case, a simple comparison of the 5% bound with the data would show whether the proportion of data lying below the bound was close enough to 5% for the bound to be judged a good description.

If there is an uncertainty associated with T_0 , however, then the definitions of the bounds become less clear. Paragraph 10.9 of ASTM E1921-21, introduces an adjustment to cover the uncertainty in T_0 associated with using a limited number of specimens. With a normal distribution and a homogeneous material, there is a 50% probability that T_0 is below the value derived from the data; a (50+34=) 84% probability the true T_0 is below the measured $T_0+1\sigma_{T_0}$; a (50+47.7=) 97.7% probability that the true T_0 is below the measured $T_0+2\sigma_{T_0}$, and so on. It is not immediately clear what e.g. the 5% bound calculated according to paragraph 10.8 means when used with a margin-adjusted T_0 , since the distributions are associated with different parameters (i.e. a distribution of K_{Jc} at constant T plus a distribution of T at constant K_{Jc}).

When a material is inhomogeneous, several approaches are possible:

- If T_{0scrn} is determined, then this is used with σ_{T_0} in the calculation of the margin-adjusted T_0 and subsequent calculations of the “5% bound”.
- Paragraph X5.3.2.7 provides a method for calculating tolerance bounds when a bimodal analysis is performed. The temperature shift of the “5% bound” is between 10°C and 35°C, depending on p_A , T_A and T_B , but not on the number of specimens investigated (i.e. not on the uncertainty on any of these parameters).
- In the multimodal analysis, the method described in paragraph X5.3.3.6 provides a tolerance bound dependent on T_m and σ_{Tm} . The temperature shift of the “5% bound” is up to 30°C for σ_{Tm} up to 35°C.

Bimodal and multimodal tolerance bounds are calculated by TOTEM software.

In the following sections, the entire FRACTESUS dataset for a given steel is used to derive lower bounds in different ways. These bounds are then compared with data from larger specimens to assess which

methods produce curves which actually bound 95% of the data from larger specimens. The next stage in the assessment considers the effect of reducing the number of 0.16T measurements involved in the prediction of bounds to more realistic levels, by considering the predictions made on the basis of individual subsets of the FRACTESUS data. The results are summarised in a Table at the end of the section for each material.

5.2 73W

The preceding sections have shown that the uncertainties on T_0 estimates are such that assessing the best way of predicting large specimen properties from 0.16T CTS data requires large sets of data from both miniature and larger specimens. A large set of data was acquired from weld 73W during the US 5th Heavy Section Steel Irradiation Program [5]. A total of 54 fracture toughness measurements were acquired from 1T-8T CTSs. 0.4T SENB (pcCv) samples of 73W were also tested by [10, 11].

Alternative methods of using the 0.16T data are illustrated below and compared with the $K_{Jc(1T)}$ data from larger specimens. (The data from the pcCv samples are plotted at 8°C above their test temperatures to compensate for the effect of specimen geometry.)

5.2.1 Using the Entire 0.16T Dataset

Figure 11a shows the entire 0.16T dataset (1T adjusted) and the median Master curve drawn using the initially-determined value of T_0 (-95.4°C) and its associated 5% lower bound. 6 of the 52 mini-CTS $K_{Jc(1T)}$ data (11%) lie below this bound, so it is slightly non-conservative for the mini-CTS data. Figure 11a also shows the “5% lower bound” using the margin-adjusted T_0 ($T_0+2\sigma_{T_0}=-95.4+9.6^\circ\text{C}$). This bounds all but 5 of the mini-CTS data, indicating that the margin adjustment does not compensate for the inhomogeneity.

Figure 11a also contains the 73W pcCv data from [10] and the CTS data. The bounds are also non-conservative with respect to these K_{Jc} data. (In the limited temperature range of the bound shown, 19 of 68 points lie below the 5% bound associated with T_0 and 10 below the 5% bound associated with $T_0+2\sigma_{T_0}$ i.e. 28% or 15% of the data in the relevant temperature range.) This is consistent with the importance of inhomogeneity seen in the comparisons between T_0 measurements from different sources.

Figure 11b uses the simplest inhomogeneity analysis by replacing T_0 with the value of T_{0scrn} measured using the entire FRACTESUS 0.16T dataset from 73W (-74.6°C). 100 of the total 106 datapoints (94%) lie above the “5% bound”, making this a good description of the data overall, if possibly conservative with respect to the 1T CTS data. (53 of 54 points, 98%, lie above the bound.) If a $2\sigma_{T_0}$ adjustment is made to T_{0scrn} , all but one of the larger-specimen points lie above the bound (99%), making it conservative.

Figure 11: Effects of simple inhomogeneity analyses of entire 0.16T CTS data set in predicting bounds to larger CTS data from 73W. (a) Median and bounds from T_0 and $(T_0+2\sigma_{T_0})$ margin-adjusted 0.16T data compared with 0.16T, pcCv, 1T CTS and 2T CTS data (b) Median and bounds based on T_{0scrn} from 0.16T data compared with 0.16T and 1T CTS data.

Since there are >20 K_{Ic} measurements in the overall FRACTESUS dataset, it is possible to perform a full homogeneity analysis. This indicates that the material is bimodal ($p_A=0.44$, $T_A=-54.1^\circ\text{C}$, $T_B=-110.9^\circ\text{C}$). The

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median and 5% bounds to the bimodal analysis (performed with TOTEM) are shown in Figure 12a. The median line is a good description of the 1T data, with T_A well within the range of T_0 values found in the larger specimens (see *Figure 6*). The 5% lower bound is a good description of the 0.16T data (94% above the bound), and possibly conservative with respect to the 1T CTS data (98% above the bound).

Figure 12: Prediction of bounds to 1T CTS data from 73W using (a) bimodal and (b) multimodal analyses of full 0.16T CTS data set.

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The multimodal analysis by TOTEM identifies $T_m = -86^\circ\text{C}$ and $\sigma_{T_m} = 36^\circ\text{C}$, which produces the median and 5% bounds shown in Figure 12b. (Figure 12b also reproduces the median and 5% bounds using the $T_{0IN} = T_{0scrn}$ procedure. This illustrates that the multimodal median and 5% bound are more widely separated than the median and bounds with the simpler inhomogeneity analysis.) The multimodal 5% curve is again a good description of the 0.16T data (94% above the bound) but conservative with respect to the 1T CTS data (no data lie below the bound).

In summary, this comparison indicates that, with a large population of 0.16T CTS-derived K_{Jc} data, margin-adjustment of the initial T_0 leads to a non-conservative prediction of the 1T CTS-derived data, but all the inhomogeneity procedures predict a “5% lower bound” which bounds 95% or more of the 1T CTS data. The simplest procedure (replacing T_0 with T_{0scrn}) is the least conservative way of extrapolating from small to large data. There is no difference in the applicability of the bounds to 0.4T, 1T or 2T data, suggesting that the scale of the material inhomogeneity in 73W is such that it affects the 0.16T samples but not the 0.4T and larger samples.

5.2.2 Using the Subsets of 0.16T Data

In general, a dataset will not contain as many as 50 datapoints, so it is useful to examine the prediction of large specimen bounds when using a smaller number of 0.16T CTS measurements.

VTT

The dataset of VTT contained $N=18$ specimens of which $r=14$ were valid and within $\pm 50^\circ\text{C}$ of the derived value of T_0 . This is a typical size of data set within FRACTESUS. The $T_0 \pm 1\sigma_{T_0}$ derived by VTT was $-107.4 \pm 6.4^\circ\text{C}$ with the data defined as inhomogeneous. This is the lowest T_0 value determined for 73W within the FRACTESUS program, and is associated with a cumulative probability of 0.19 (based on the normal distribution fitted in Figure 4).

Figure 13a shows the 0.16T 73W data from VTT and the median, 5% and 1% curves based on T_{0scrn} (-95.8°C) derived from these data. The “5% bound” is slightly non-conservative with respect to the 0.16T data (2 points rather than one lie below the bound). The Figure also shows the 1T data, for which the 5% bound based on the 0.16T T_{0scrn} alone is clearly non-conservative, as the 1T data are scattered about the “5% lower bound” rather than the median. The “1% lower bound” (as favoured by [7]) is a better descriptor of the large specimen data.

Figure 13: Effect of simple T_{oscrn} inhomogeneity analysis of VTT 73W data on predicting bounds to 1T CTS data. (a) Bounds calculated using T_{oscrn} (b) $1\sigma_{T0}$ and $2\sigma_{T0}$ margin-adjustment of T_{oscrn} bounds.

Using the $1\sigma_{T_0}$ (6.4°C) margin adjustment in addition to $T_{0\text{scrn}}$ improves the description of the 1T data, but the “5% lower bound” still does not even bound 80% of the data. With a $2\sigma_{T_0}$ margin adjustment to $T_{0\text{scrn}}$, the nominal 5% line bounds all but 2 (89%) of the 0.16T data and all but 7 (88%) of the 1T data. Even this adjustment leaves the “5% bound” slightly non-conservative.

CIEMAT

Figure 14 shows the equivalent results for the 0.16T data from CIEMAT ($T_0 \pm 1\sigma_{T_0} = -97.3 \pm 7.2$, cumulative probability = 0.31, inhomogeneous, $T_{0\text{scrn}} = -80.9^\circ\text{C}$).

In this case, the “5% bound” calculated using $T_{0\text{scrn}}$ derived from the 0.16T data bounds all but 6 of the 1T data (11%), while the “1% bound” lies below all the data. The “5% bounds” calculated using either $T_{0\text{scrn}} + 1\sigma_{T_0}$ or $T_{0\text{scrn}} + 2\sigma_{T_0}$ bound all but 1 of the 1T data (2%). For this subset of 0.16T data, extrapolation using the $2\sigma_{T_0}$ margin adjustment to $T_{0\text{scrn}}$ is, thus a reasonable description of the lower bound to the 1T data.

Figure 14: Effect of simple $T_{0\text{scrn}}$ inhomogeneity analysis of CIEMAT 73W data on predicting bounds to 1T CTS data.

HZDR

The HZDR data ($T_0 \pm 1\sigma_{T_0} = -97.3 \pm 7.2$, cumulative probability=0.40) were calculated as homogeneous. In consequence, no inhomogeneity analysis would be performed if these were the only data available. Instead, margin adjustment of T_0 must be used to predict the large-CTS data.

Figure 15 shows that the straightforward 5% bound calculated using the value of T_0 derived from the 0.16T data bounds about 60% of the 1T CTS data. The “5% bound” calculated using the margin-adjusted $T_0 + 1\sigma_{T_0}$ margin bounds all but 10 of the 1T data (18%), while the “5% bound” calculated using the margin-adjusted $T_0 + 2\sigma_{T_0}$ bounds all but 3 of the 1T data (6%). For the HZDR subset, therefore, the margin-adjustment analysis of the 0.16T data provides a good prediction of the 1T data. (Note that the HZDR T_0 value lies close to overall mini- T_0 value.)

Figure 15: Effect of analysis of HZDR 73W 0.16T CTS data on predicting bounds to 1T CTS data.

SCK.CEN

The 0.16T data from SCK.CEN ($T_0 \pm 1\sigma_{T_0} = -75.5 \pm 7.2$, cumulative probability=0.64, inhomogeneous, $T_{0scrn} = -65.9^\circ\text{C}$) are shown in Figure 16. As this data set is determined to be inhomogeneous, and contains 15 points, it was possible to perform the simple inhomogeneity analysis and define T_{0scrn} as T_{0IN} . The “5% bounds” derived using T_{0scrn} , $T_{0scrn} + 1\sigma_{T_0}$ and $T_{0scrn} + 2\sigma_{T_0}$ are also shown in Figure 16, together with the 1T data. All but 1 of the 15 0.16T measurements (93%) lie above the 5% bound making this a good description of the 0.16T data. All but 1 of the 54 1T data lie above the 5% lower bound calculated using

T_{0scrn} (98%) and all lie above the margin-adjusted bounds making the predictions conservative with respect to the 1T data.

Figure 16: Effect of simple T_{0scrn} inhomogeneity analysis of SCK.CEN 73W data on predicting bounds to 1T CTS data.

UoB

The data set from the University of Birmingham was too small ($N=7$) for the T_0 measurement to be valid, but it was included in the distribution of T_0 values as the highest of the values ($T_0 \pm 1\sigma_{T_0} = -51.0 \pm 9.3$, cumulative probability=0.90, inhomogeneous, $T_{0scrn} = -30.3^\circ\text{C}$). Following the simple inhomogeneity procedure for fewer than 9 specimens, produced $T_{0IN} = T_{0scrn}$.

Figure 17 shows that using the simple inhomogeneity analysis the “5% bound” is an extremely conservative bound to the 1T CTS data.

Figure 17: Effect of simple T_{0scrn} inhomogeneity analysis of SCK.CEN 73W data on predicting bounds to 1T CTS data.

Data from Chaouadi [6]

Chaouadi investigated specimen size effects in 73W in 1998, using the HSSI $\geq 1T$ CTS data as the reference case and 20% side-grooved pcCv (0.4T), half- (0.32T) and sub-sized pcCv (0.2T) geometries as the small samples. The reference case was established by performing Master curve analyses of subsets of the HSSI data as illustrated in Figure 18. The Gaussian fitted to the frequency distribution appears to have a 1σ value of around $\pm 3^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 18: Frequency distribution of T_0 based on Monte Carlo simulations of HSSI 73W $\geq 1T$ data : 12 data points from a population of 78 valid K_{Ic} measurements replicated 1000 times [6].

This project has received funding from the Euratom research and training programme 2020-2024 under grant agreement No. 900014.

The data from all specimen sizes are shown in Figure 19, which shows 27 measurements from the 0.4T samples, 10 from the 0.32T and 10 from the 0.2T samples. Most of the pcCv data (38 of 47) were rendered invalid by excess plasticity, so effective T_0 values could be calculated only if invalid data (though not those with excess ductile crack extension) were treated as valid. With this procedure, the T_0 values for the small specimens were -63.5°C (0.4T) -60.3°C (0.32T) and -65.7°C (0.2T) with $N=6$ in each case. Given that the excess plasticity would push the derived T_0 to higher values, these may be considered overestimates of the T_0 values associated with the small specimen geometries. Compensating for the effect of the pcCv geometry, however, would push the T_0 associated with a CTS of equivalent thickness to higher values.

Comparing the as-cited pcCv-derived values with the FRACTESUS 0.16T data, T_0 values of -60.3 to -65.7°C lie in the range 0.76-0.83 in the cumulative probability distribution. They are also within -2σ of the distribution shown in Figure 18. It is, thus, difficult to decide whether Chaouadi's 0.2T-0.4T data lie in the same distribution as the $\geq 1T$ CTS data or the 0.16T data of Figure 18. With so few pcCv data in Chaouadi's dataset, it is also not possible to perform an inhomogeneity analysis. The pcCv data from [6] thus do not clarify whether the effect of inhomogeneity seen in the microstructure (Figure 7) and in the overall 0.16T dataset only affects measurements in 0.16T specimens or would also have affected 0.2T-0.4T specimens.

The bounds in Figure 19 are drawn using the 0.32T value of T_0 (derived from 6 measurements) of -60.3°C . The 5% lower bound appears slightly conservative with respect to the CTS data, as would be expected for an estimate of T_0 which was higher than the average of the FRACTESUS subsets.

Figure 19: Comparison between Mastercurve bounds derived from six K_{Ic} measurements on half-pCCv specimens data acquired from larger specimens of 73W [6].

Based on his data, Chaouadi concluded that specimens down to 0.2T would yield consistent estimates of T_0 . Based on the larger and more valid datasets acquired within FRACTESUS, however, the results appear serendipitous.

5.2.3 Summary

The subsets of the 0.16T CTS data produced by the different laboratories in the FRACTESUS program produce a distribution of T_0 values. Not all subsets are inhomogeneous, so different procedures must be used to predict bounds from the various subsets. Using the applicable procedures for each subset results in a range of predictions of the bounds to the 1T CTS data which range from very non-conservative to very conservative, as summarised in Table 4.

Table 4. Relation between 1T data from 73W and “5% bounds” derived from 0.16T data using different definitions of the DBTT.

Set	“5% bound” calculated based on					
	T_0	$T_0+2\sigma_{T_0}$	T_{0scrn}	$T_{0scrn}+2\sigma_{T_0}$	Bimodal T_0	T_m
All	N	N	G	C	G	C
VTT			N	N	-	-
CIEMAT			N	G	-	-
HZDR	N	G			-	-
SCK.CEN			G	C	-	-
UoB	G		O	O	-	-

N=non-conservative (fewer than 92% of data above the “5% bound”);

G=reasonably good description of data (92-98% of data above the “5% bound”);

C= conservative (more than 98% of data above bound, but data present below or close to bound);

O=overly conservative (all data clearly above bound);

- no analysis possible.

Comparing results from the subsets with those from the overall dataset suggests that the number of 0.16T CTSs required to compensate for material inhomogeneity at the scale shown in *Figure 7* is greater than the numbers in any of the FRACTESUS subsets. Where data from the literature involve smaller numbers of (less valid) measurements than those used within FRACTESUS, conclusions based on those data will be associated with significant uncertainty and should be treated with caution.

5.3 JRQ

The A533B plate JRQ was used in several IAEA Coordinated Research Programs. The data used here were measured on 0.5T CTSs by AEA Technology, VTT and NRI řež during CRP3 and reported in [12], the pcCv data were acquired by KAERI [13], 0.4T and 0.5T CTS data were acquired by CIEMAT during CRP5 [14] and 1T CTS data were acquired by multiple laboratories during CRP5 [8]. This large specimen dataset contains a total of 135 K_{Jc} measurements from specimens of sizes up to and including 0.5T CTSs and a further 95 measurements using 1T CTSs.

The 1T-adjusted K_{Jc} measurements from FRACTESUS and the various IAEA CRPs are shown in Figure 20, with the pcCv data plotted at 8°C above the test temperature to account for the geometry effect. There is a strong overlap between the valid FRACTESUS data and data from larger samples.

Figure 20: Comparison between FRACTESUS and IAEA data from JRQ.

5.3.1 Using the Entire FRACTESUS JRQ 0.16T Dataset

The data from large specimens up to 0.5T CTS are shown in Figure 21, together with the median lines and 5% bounds associated with T_0 and T_{0scrn} derived from the FRACTESUS K_{Jc} measurements. The FRACTESUS measurements themselves are excluded so that the bounds predicted from the 0.16T data can be more clearly compared with the larger specimen IAEA data. Figure 21 shows the 50% and 5% trend lines predicted from the initial value of T_0 (-61.8°C) and also when T_{0scrn} is used in place of T_0 . (The

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margin-adjusted 5% bound using the initial $T_0+2\sigma_{T_0}$ is less than 1°C from the 5% bound using $T_{0\text{scrn}}$, so is not drawn in.) All but 15 measurements (89%) lie above the initial 5% bound and all but 10 measurements (93%) lie above the “margin-adjusted 5% bound” or the “5% bound” associated with $T_{0\text{scrn}}$. The simple inhomogeneity analysis of the complete 0.16T dataset thus leads to a good description of the larger specimen data for sizes up to and including 0.5T CTS.

Figure 21: Comparison between bounds predicted from 0.16T CTS measurements on JRQ and distribution of JRQ data from specimens up to 0.5T CTSs.

Figure 22 then compares the same bounds with only the 1T CTS data from CRP5. In this case, all but 22 measurements (77% of the 95 measurements) lie above the initial 5% bound and all but 13 measurements (86%) lie above the “5% bound” associated with $T_{0\text{scrn}}$ (or $T_0+2\sigma_{T_0}$). The bounds derived from the 0.16T data are, thus, more consistent with data from 0.4T and 0.5T specimens than with the data from 1T specimens. This is consistent with the bias in T_0 distributions shown in Figure 8, in which the 0.16T T_0 data were directly consistent with the pcCv T_0 data, but not with the 1T data. This suggests that, in the case of JRQ, the scale of the material inhomogeneity is such that it affects all specimen geometries with crack fronts up to 12.5mm in a similar way. It is only between 12.5mm and 25mm that the crack front begins to sample representative amounts of all constituents of the microstructure.

Figure 22: Comparison between bounds predicted from 0.16T CTS measurements on JRQ and distribution of JRQ data from 1T CTSs.

Figure 23: Comparison between 5% bounds derived from bimodal and multimodal analyses of FRACTESUS 0.16T data and K_{Ic} measurements on larger samples.

The results of the bimodal and multimodal analyses of the FRACTESUS 0.16T CTS data are shown in Figure 23. In this case, all but 8 of the 95 1T CTS measurements (92%) lie above the bimodal 5% bound and all but 5 (95%) lie above the multimodal 5% bound. Both of these bounds are better descriptors of the 1T data than the margin-adjusted or T_{0scrn} bounds, with the multimodal bound being the best description.

5.3.2 Using the Subsets of JRQ 0.16T Data

Some of the subsets of 0.16T data were identified as homogeneous and some as inhomogeneous, as outlined in Table 5. For the homogeneous datasets, the $2\sigma_{T_0}$ -margin-adjusted T_0 is used to predict the lower bounds to the larger specimen data, while T_{0scrn} is used for the inhomogeneous datasets. The chosen value of the reference temperature to be used for lower bound estimation is indicated by the numbers in bold.

The reference temperatures in Table 5 range from -37.2°C (PSI) to -53.3°C (CRIEPI). The “5% lower bounds” associated with these limiting DBTT values are shown in Figure 24, where they are compared with all the large specimen data including the 1T CTS data. 19 points (9%) lie below the CRIEPI bound and 7 (3%) below the PSI bound. The predictions from the sub-sets thus range from non-conservative to good, as summarised in Table 6.

Table 5: Characteristics of 0.16T CTS JRQ subsets.

Data set	T_0 ($^\circ\text{C}$)	σ_{T_0} ($^\circ\text{C}$)	$T_0+2\sigma_{T_0}$ ($^\circ\text{C}$)	T_{0scrn} ($^\circ\text{C}$)	r	N	$\sum n_i r_i$	Inhomogeneous?
UJV	-61.5	6.2	-49.1	-46.3	18	24	2.45	Yes
HZDR	-66.4	6.6	-53.2	-63.9	12	25	1.9	No
BZN	-54.4	7.4	-39.6	-54.4	9	12	1.29	No
PSI	-50.4	6.6	-37.2	-47.5	13	16	1.76	No
CCFE	-65.4	6.2	-53	-50.5	16	16	2.21	Yes
CRIEPI	-65.1	5.8	-53.5	-53.3	23	24	3.32	Yes

If only the specimens up to 0.5T CTS are considered, using any of the 0.16T JRQ subsets in accordance with ASTM E1921-21 Appendix X5 will lead to a good prediction of the behaviour of the larger specimens. If the 1T data are included, however, only the predictions based on two thirds of the subsets will be reasonable descriptions of the larger specimen data; the remainder will lead to non-conservative descriptions. Even so, the degree of non-conservatism is less severe than was the case for 73W.

Figure 24: Comparison between bounds based on 0.16T subsets (only highest and lowest values shown) and measurements from larger specimens of JRQ.

Table 6. Relation between large specimen data from JRQ and “5% bounds” derived from 0.16T data using different definitions of the DBTT.

FRACTESUS Set	Larger set	“5% bound” calculated based on					
		T ₀	T ₀ +2σ _{T0}	T _{0scrn}	T _{0scrn} +2σ _{T0}	Bimodal T ₀	T _m
All	≤0.5T	N	G	G	G	-	-
	1T	N	N	N	N	G	G
CRIEPI	All			N	G		
UKAEA				N	G		
HZDR			G				
UJV				G	G		
BZN			G				
PSI			G				

N=non-conservative; G=reasonably good description of data; G/C= good or slightly conservative; C= conservative; O=overly conservative; - no analysis possible.

5.4 15Kh2MFAA

The 15Kh2MFAA CrMoV forging used in FRACTESUS came from RPV core shell ring 0.3.1 of the Greifswald Unit 8 WWER-440 reactor which was built but not commissioned. It has been studied in several campaigns and K_{Ic} data were provided to NNL by E. Altstadt of HZDR within FRACTESUS. The measurements were performed on 20% side-grooved specimens, 110 on pcCv specimens (82 in one campaign and 28 in another) 15 on 0.5T CTSs and 7 on 1T CTSs.

The 1T-adjusted K_{Ic} measurements are shown in *Figure 25*, together with the FRACTESUS data. Data from the smaller specimens appear to show more scatter than those from the larger specimens. There is no evident difference between the datasets within scatter. The range of test temperatures used for the larger specimens is narrower than for 73W and JRQ, with a greater overlap between the test temperatures used for 0.16T and larger specimens.

Figure 25: Comparison between FRACTESUS and larger data from 15Kh2MFAA.

5.4.1 Using the Entire FRACTESUS 15Kh2MFAA 0.16T Dataset

The 0.5T and 1T data are replotted in Figure 26, together with the pcCv data shifted by 8°C. Since the combined 0.16T CTS data set was defined as inhomogeneous, the 50% and 5% bounds associated with T_{0scrn} are also drawn on the plot. The 50% line derived from the 0.16T data is a somewhat conservative

description of the larger specimen data, but the simple “5% bound” is a good description of the data distribution: 7 of 132 points (5%) lie below the “5% bound” based on T_{0scrn} . This good agreement is as expected from *Figure 1* to which the 15Kh2MFAA data contribute the lowest T_0 measurements, sitting within 1°C of the one-to-one line.

Figure 26. Comparison between large specimen 15Kh2MFAA data and bounds predicted by simple analyses of entire FRACTESUS dataset and from subsets producing the lowest and highest T_0 or T_{0scrn} (as appropriate). The pcCv data are shifted by 8°C .

The summary of the comparisons is shown in Table 8.

5.4.2 Investigating Different Margin Adjustments And Using Subsets of the Data from FRACTESUS 15Kh2MFAA 0.16T Samples

As illustrated in *Figure 4*, the individual sub-sets of the 0.16T data provided T_0 values which were distributed about the mean with a $1\sigma_N$ of $\pm 13^\circ\text{C}$, so it is unsurprising that the “5% bounds” derived from the subsets also show a range. The characteristics of the subsets are shown in Table 7.

The lowest reference temperature (T_0) value was associated with the homogeneous EK-CER sub-set and the highest (T_{0scrn}) was associated with the inhomogeneous UJV subset. Figure 26 therefore also shows the 5% bounds associated with T_0 for EK-CER and T_{0scrn} for UJV to illustrate the range in bounds to be expected when analysing medium-sized datasets according to ASTM E1921-21. The “5% bounds”

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derived from subset predictions of T_0 / T_{0scrn} range from slightly conservative to very non-conservative (2% - 16% of data below the associated “5% bounds”) with respect to the larger specimen K_{Jc} data.

Table 7: Characteristics of 0.16T CTS 15Kh2MFAA subsets.

Data set	T_0 (°C)	σT_0 (°C)	$T_0 + 2\sigma T_0$ (°C)	T_{0scrn} (°C)	r	N	$\Sigma n_i r_i$	Inhomogeneous?
SCK-CEN	-91.7	6.7	-78.3	-77.6	12	16	1.68	Yes
UJV	-82.7	6.4	-69.9	-48.8	16	18	2.11	Yes
VTT	-110.0	6.4	-97.2	-73.8	14	21	2.00	Yes
HZDR	-90.3	6.1	-78.1	-79.4	17	20	2.40	Yes
EK-CER	-108.1	6.6	-94.9	-108.1	13	14	1.98	No
CRIEPI	-94.5	5.9	-82.7	-77	19	21	2.84	Yes

The margin adjustment to T_0 , described in paragraph 10.9 of ASTM E1921-21 is intended to non-conservative predictions caused by the uncertainty on T_0 . Figure 27 therefore investigates the effect of using different types of margins on the relation between the large specimen data and the “5% bounds” associated with margin-adjusted reference temperatures. Figure 27a adjusts T_0 (or T_{0scrn}) values from the 0.16T CTS data by $2\sigma_{T_0}$, while Figure 27b uses $2\sigma_{total}$. The material inhomogeneity contribution to the uncertainty on T_0 was calculated to be 11.33°C for 15Kh2MFAA, as reported in Table 2. The assessment in Figure 27b is intended to show what would happen in the manipulation of results from a previously-uncharacterised material, so the generic estimate for base metals, 7°C, is used instead of the measured, material-specific value.

The bounds in Figure 27a based on the entire FRACTESUS dataset and $2\sigma_{T_0}$ are a slightly more conservative description of the larger specimen data (96% above the “5% bound”) than without margin-adjustment (95% above the bound), but the description is still good. Considering predictions based on the 0.16T data subsets and the $2\sigma_{T_0}$ margin-adjusted reference temperatures, the “5% bounds” in Figure 27a still range from conservative to non-conservative (2% and 13% of data below the bounds).

When the margin adjustment is made using $2\sigma_{total}$, Figure 27b shows that the predicted “5% bounds” become slightly more conservative, but still range from conservative to non-conservative (1% of the large specimen data lie below the UJV bound, and 9% below the EK-CER bound). More detail is summarized in Table 8, indicating that, while the effect of using the FRACTESUS subsets is to cause the prediction of the “5% lower bound” to range from conservative to non-conservative, most predictions are good.

Figure 27. Effect of margin-adjustments on comparison between large specimen data and 5% bounds predicted from 0.16T CTS data (a) margin= $2\sigma_{T0}$ (b) margin= $2\sigma_{total}$.

In summary, using either form of margin adjustment makes the predictions of the bounds to the large specimen data slightly more conservative, but does not alter their categorization.

Table 8. Relation between large specimen data from 15Kh2MFAA and “5% bounds” derived from 0.16T data using different definitions of the DBTT.

Set	5% bound based on							
	T_0	$T_0+2\sigma_{T_0}$	$T_0+2\sigma_{Total}$	T_{0scrn}	$T_{0scrn}+2\sigma_{T_0}$	$T_{0scrn}+2\sigma_{Total}$	Bimodal T_0	T_m
All				G	G	G	C	C
EK-CER	N	N	N			N		
HZDR				G	G			
SCK-CEN				G	G			
CRIEPI				G	G			
VTT				G	G			
UJV				C	C	C		

6 Summary and Discussion

The potential advantage of using miniature CTSs to characterise material toughness and the DBTT is that a smaller total volume of material is required than when using large samples. This is true even if the same total crack length is tested in miniature and larger samples. Further advantages are offered to nuclear plant operators as the problems of gamma heating and dose attenuation within a sample are significantly reduced with a smaller specimen. In addition, up to eight 0.16T CTSs can be cut from a single Charpy specimen, allowing the conversion of reactor pressure vessel surveillance schemes historically designed to provide Charpy data into schemes providing toughness data.

The potential disadvantages of using miniature CTSs include:

- the difficulties in manufacturing and testing such small samples, especially from irradiated material.
This was assessed in D3.3 [2] and it was clear that the problem could be minimised by careful training of personnel.
- the requirement of testing at lower temperatures to ensure that sufficient uncensored data were acquired for a T_0 measurement to be valid.
This was also assessed in D3.3 [2]. Even with experience and the careful selection of test temperatures in line with the procedures described in paragraphs 8.4 and 10.3.1 of ASTM E1921-21, up to 25% of 0.16T CTS data were likely to be invalid. This highlighted the importance of increasing the numbers of specimens tested when reducing the specimen size. (A possible method of compensating for excessive plasticity was investigated in D3.3, but it was concluded that this should be used as a way of obtaining indicative measurements from otherwise unusable data, rather than as a procedure for common use.)

- the non-representative nature of the data acquired.

This is the main subject of the current report and is discussed further below.

One aim of the FRACTESUS program has been to allay the concerns of potential users of toughness data acquired using 0.16T CTSs, that the information is equivalent to that acquired from standard, 1T CTSs. Work Package 1 of FRACTESUS included a survey of [15], which identified that the representativity of the data was a concern to many stakeholders. They felt that a toughness measurement from a miniature specimen could be valid in itself, but that the volume of material tested might be too small to be properly representative of the material. The FRACTESUS program was designed to investigate this issue by incorporating both base metals, which were anticipated to be relatively homogeneous, and welds, which were expected to be less homogeneous.

The overall comparisons between the values of T_0 derived from 0.16T CTS specimens and larger specimens (*Figure 1 - Figure 3*) showed that the values were generally consistent within $\pm 2\sigma_{T_0}$. This initially suggested that measurements on 0.16T were adequate to predict T_0 for RPV steels. Examination of the cases in which the 0.16T T_0 measurements were not good predictors, however, indicated that they corresponded with situations in which the 0.16T data are identified as inhomogeneous, while the larger specimen data are defined as homogeneous. The trend for the 0.16T data to predict lower (non-conservative) T_0 values than the larger samples in these cases then highlighted the importance of identifying when material inhomogeneity might affect the toughness data and, most particularly, how to compensate for its effect. It is important to note that this inhomogeneity is in addition to that associated with a random spatial distribution of a population of weak links (with a distribution of strengths in the population): the $B^{0.25}$ size-correction accounts for that contribution to scatter in the $K_{Jc,1T}$ data. The inhomogeneity of interest is that with variations in the microstructure which result in multiple different, spatially-separated populations of weak links. It is also important to note that this inhomogeneity affects data from both miniature and larger specimens.

The analysis of T_0 values measured in 0.16T CTSs and in larger specimens of two RPV steels shows that σ_{T_0} , as identified in ASTM E1921-21 paragraph 10.9, is insufficient to describe the variability in T_0 in either small or large specimens. The influence of material inhomogeneity increased the range in T_0 values measured in different experiments on the same material and geometry by up to 25°C. This is consistent with the magnitude of effects of inhomogeneity on T_0 anticipated in Appendix X5 of ASTM E1921-21.

The analysis of T_0 values also shows that material inhomogeneity can affect different sizes of sample in different ways, depending on whether the crack front can sample a representative range of microstructures or may only sample a single constituent. The behaviour of the $K_{Jc,1T}$ measurements and the metallography show that it cannot be assumed that even a base metal, tested between $\frac{1}{4}t$ and $\frac{3}{4}t$, will necessarily be homogeneous on the scale of a test specimen crack front.

It is important to note that the scale of the relevant inhomogeneity differs in different steels. The scale of the material inhomogeneities seen in this project are such that 0.16T specimens frequently sampled single constituents of the microstructure, producing an inhomogeneous distribution of $K_{Jc,1T}$ measurements. Conversely, the >1T specimens always sampled all constituents of the microstructure,

producing a homogeneous distribution of $K_{Jc,1T}$ measurements. In one material examined in detail (73W), the change in behaviour occurred below 1T while the other (JRQ), it appeared to occur above 1T.

This observation affects the interpretation of comparisons performed in the literature in which 0.16T data are compared with pcCv or 0.5T data to determine whether miniature and larger specimens produce equivalent data. Depending on the scale of the material inhomogeneity, consistency between 0.16T and 0.4T or 0.5T data, or even between pcCv and 0.5T CTS data, may or may not predicate consistency between $<1T$ and $\geq 1T$ specimen data.

Once the significance of material inhomogeneity is recognised, it is possible to identify the effects of the scale and prevalence of the weaker microstructural constituent (family of links) on the relation between small and large specimens. The anticipated effects are summarised in Table 9.

Two situations are considered in Table 9: in the first, the total crack front length is kept constant, but the individual samples may be either 1T or 0.16T; in the second, the number of samples is kept constant. The two situations help to distinguish between simple specimen size effects and the effects of testing shorter overall crack fronts. They represent the extremes of data sets likely to be encountered in practical comparisons between 0.16T and larger specimens. In both situations, the total volume of material required is smaller with the smaller specimens (much smaller in the second situation).

Variations in the scale of the material inhomogeneity are then considered: it may be such that the weaker constituent is present in all large samples or only some large samples and in all, some or no small samples.

Table 9. Effects of material inhomogeneity on homogeneity of K_{Jc} data in small and large specimens, and consequent predictability of T_0 in large specimens based on 0.16T data.

Option 1: Equal crack front lengths				
Specimen Size	1T	0.16T		
Number of specimens	8	50		
1a More frequent appearance of weaker constituent				
Presence of weaker constituent	In all samples	In all samples	In some samples	In no samples
Homogeneous/Inhomogeneous $K_{Jc,1T}$ distribution	Hom	Hom	Inhom	(will not occur)
Large-T_0 - mini-T_0		0	>0	"
Large-T_{0scrn} - mini-T_{0scrn}		-*	0	"
1b Less frequent appearance of weaker constituent				
Presence of weaker constituent	In some samples	All	Some	None
Homogeneous/Inhomogeneous	Inhom	-	Inhom	(will not occur)
Large-T_0 - mini-T_0	-	-	>0	"
Large-T_{0scrn} - mini-T_{0scrn}	-	-	0 if frequency of occurrence is great enough in 0.16T CTSs for screening procedure to work effectively, otherwise >0	"
Option 2: Equal numbers of specimens				
Specimen Size	1T	0.16T		
Number of specimens	8	8		
2a More frequent appearance of weaker constituent				
Presence of weaker constituent	In all samples	All	Some	None
Homogeneous/Inhomogeneous	Hom	Hom	Inhom	Hom
Large-T_0 - mini-T_0	-	0	>0	>0
Large-T_{0scrn} - mini-T_{0scrn}	-	-	0	(will not occur)
2b Less frequent appearance of weaker constituent				
Presence of weaker constituent	In some samples	All	Some	None
Homogeneous/Inhomogeneous	Inhom	-	Inhom	Hom
Large-T_0 - mini-T_0		-	<0 or >0	>0
Large-T_{0scrn} - mini-T_{0scrn}		-	0	(will not occur)

* indicates that the situation cannot occur or the analysis is not performed

For example, Table 9 shows that, if the weaker constituent is present in all 1T samples and the total crack front length is kept constant (Option 1a), then (depending on the constituent distribution) the weak constituent may also be present in all or only some of the 0.16T samples. If, however, the number of 0.16T samples is too small (Option 2a), then it is possible that none of the 0.16T samples will contain the weak constituent. As a result, when the 1T measurements appear homogeneous, the 0.16T measurements may appear either homogeneous or inhomogeneous. If the 1T data are homogeneous and the 0.16T data are inhomogeneous, then the large- T_0 values will be higher than the mini- T_0 values, but application of the inhomogeneity analysis should correct this. If both the 1T data and 0.16T data are homogeneous then, with equal crack front lengths (Option 1a), the T_0 values will be the same. If, however, the specimen numbers are the same (Option 2a), the short overall crack front makes it possible for the 0.16T data to appear homogeneous only because the weak constituent happens always to be absent. In this situation, the 0.16T data will be non-conservative and there will be no obvious way to correct them. This situation is indicated in red in Table 9.

When the scale of the inhomogeneity is such that the weaker constituent is not always present even in the 1T samples (Options 1b and 2b), then it is not possible for it to be present in all 0.16T samples. With equal crack front lengths then (Option 1b) both the 1T and 0.16T data will be inhomogeneous: their T_0 values may or may not match, but the inhomogeneity-corrected T_0 values should match (if the number of datapoints exhibiting inhomogeneity are sufficient to trigger the inhomogeneity analysis). With small numbers of 0.16T specimens (Option 2b), the 0.16T data may all exclude the weaker constituent, whereupon the 0.16T data will appear homogeneous, but will lead to a non-conservative estimate of large- T_0 .

In further illustration of this assessment, Table 10 reproduces Table 36 of [2], summarising results for JRQ. The 1T data are homogeneous, but the data from smaller samples may be homogeneous or inhomogeneous. The combined dataset (a large overall crack front, although not as large as for the 1T specimens) and the UJV, CRIEPI and UKAEA subsets are all inhomogeneous and yield T_{0scrn} values within $2\sigma_{T_0}$ of the 1T-derived T_0 . The homogeneous HZDR and pcCv data (12 and 9 valid measurements respectively) yield T_0 values which are non-conservative with respect to the 1T data while the homogeneous BZN data (9 valid measurements) yield a consistent T_0 value. JRQ thus appears to behave in accordance with Option 2a of Table 9.

In summary, with equal crack front lengths / very large numbers of 0.16T specimens, the DBTTs of 0.16T and 1T specimens should be equivalent but, if only small numbers of 0.16T specimens are tested, then apparently homogeneous 0.16T datasets may yield non-conservative estimates of T_0 . ***The necessity for the FRACTESUS program is, thus, to identify how large a number of 0.16T specimens must be tested to avoid these non-conservative estimates of T_0 .***

Table 10. Characteristics of measurements on JRQ [2].

Data set	T_0 (°C)	σ_{T0} (K)	$T_{0,scrn}$ (°C)	r	N	$\sum n_i \cdot r_i$	Inhom
UJV	-61.5	6.2	-46.4	18	24	2.45	Yes
HZDR	-66.9	6.6	-63.9	12	25	1.90	No
BZN	-54.4	7.4	-54.4	9	12	1.29	No
PSI	-50.4	6.6	-47.5	13	16	1.76	No
CRIEPI	-65.1	5.8	-53.3	23	24	3.32	Yes
UKAEA	-65.4	6.2	-50.5	16	16	2.21	Yes
Combined MCT data	-61.7	4.4	-54.0	95	120	13.1	Yes
Larger specimens 1T-CT [15]	-53.6	3.1	-41.3	69	83	10.7	No
Larger specimens PCCv [16]	-65.6	6.0	-65.6	9	10	1.40	No

The investigation of the effects of material inhomogeneity on the transferability of data from 0.16T to 1T and larger specimens continued with an assessment of the predictability of the lower bounds to the large specimen K_{Jc} data using parameters derived from analysis of the 0.16T CTS data. The 1T CTS K_{Jc} data for both JRQ and 73W were not well-described by “5% lower bounds” determined using T_0 or the $2\sigma_{T0}$ -margin-adjusted T_0 derived from the combined FRACTESUS K_{Jc} datasets, according to paragraph 10.9.2 of ASTM E1921-21. It was necessary to use the inhomogeneity analyses of the 0.16T data to produce lower bounds which were applicable to the $\geq 1T$ data. For 73W, the “5% bound” calculated using T_{0scrn} described the 1T data well, while the bimodal and multimodal bounds were more conservative. For JRQ, the T_{0scrn} “5% bound” was slightly non-conservative for the 1T data, while the bimodal and multimodal analyses were much better descriptions of the 1T data.

These observations indicate that, if the 0.16T dataset contains many measurements and a full inhomogeneity analysis is performed, then the outcome will be a good or conservative prediction of the lower bounds to $\geq 1T$ data. “Many” in this case refers to the combined datasets for the FRACTESUS steels, which contained between 42 and 120 measurements each ($r=33-95$). With such large datasets, it is very likely that the full range of microstructures will be present along the combined crack front. If, however, the samples have all been cut in a particular location, then even such large numbers of small samples may not contain a sufficient range of microstructures to be representative of the bulk material. Cutting samples from as wide a variety of locations as possible will enhance the likelihood of picking up representative levels of inhomogeneity.

The suggested number of specimens tested by each participant in FRACTESUS was at least 16. This was greater than is often seen in the literature. The data were analysed using TOTEM software, which requires >20 K_{Jc} values before the bimodal or multimodal calculations are performed (in accordance with the assessment in ASTM E1921-21 paragraph 10.6.4 that the inhomogeneity assessment is not reliable with fewer data points). In consequence, only 5 of the 23 subsets of the data contained sufficient measurements to perform a full homogeneity analysis. The effect of the relatively small numbers of specimens in the subsets was that the inhomogeneity assessment could only yield a value for T_{0scrn} . Predictions of lower bounds based on individual subsets and T_{0scrn} then ranged from conservative with respect to the $\geq 1T$ data to non-conservative. In the case of 73W, the range was from very conservative

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to very non-conservative. **The necessity for the FRACTESUS program is, thus, to identify how best to deal with the likelihood of inhomogeneity at the <25mm scale without excess conservatism.**

Hall et al. [16] have proposed that the inhomogeneity analysis of paragraph X5.2.1 in ASTM E1921-21, be applied to datasets with $N \leq 20$, rather than the $N \leq 9$ required by ASTM E1921-21. (See Section 4.1 for details.) They also propose that, when T_{0max} is used in place of T_{0scrn} , no margin adjustment need be made. Using this procedure on the FRACTESUS subsets from 73W and JRQ which were inhomogeneous would replace T_{0scrn} with T_{0max} in all but two cases. Comparing T_{0max} with the margin-adjusted T_{0scrn} for the remaining subsets produces an average value of

$$T_{0max} - (T_{0scrn} + 2\sigma_{T0}) = 39 \pm 39^\circ\text{C} \text{ and}$$

$$T_{0max} - (T_{0scrn} + 2\sigma_{total}) = 21 \pm 45^\circ\text{C}$$

This shows that the procedure suggested by Hall et al. is generally more conservative than using a $2\sigma_{total}$ adjustment. Table 4, Table 6 and Table 8 show that the margin-adjusted T_{0scrn} values derived from 0.16T subsets are predominantly good or conservative descriptions of the larger data, with two non-conservative cases and one overly-conservative case. Strangely, replacing $T_{0scrn} + 2\sigma_{T0}$ with T_{0max} does increase the conservatism of most of the predictions of the 5% bound to the large specimen data, but does not remove all the non-conservative predictions.

The predictions of bounds within this study, make it clear that, with an RPV steel of unknown T_0 and unknown degree / scale of inhomogeneity, it would be impossible to say whether a T_{0scrn} derived from a K_{Jc} dataset of around 16 0.16T measurements would lead to conservative or non-conservative predictions of the bounds to 1T data. It would be better practice to test sufficient 0.16T specimens that the full inhomogeneity analysis can be used reliably to predict the bounds. The smallest “large” dataset within FRACTESUS, used successfully to predict data, contained 30 measurements. At this stage in the FRACTESUS program, therefore, a suitable dataset might require up to 30 specimens. The effect of using fewer than 30 specimens could be examined further using statistical analyses of the combined FRACTESUS datasets, but will not be performed for this report. **The best practice suggested by the current analysis of 0.16T data is, thus, to test at least 30 0.16T CTSs and to perform an inhomogeneity analysis, using the 5% lower bound associated with T_m to predict the behaviour of larger samples without excess conservatism.**

As discussed in the Introduction, the miniaturisation of toughness specimens has arisen in part because of the scarcity of test material, most particularly irradiated test material. In consequence, a test program requiring 20-30 specimens may not be possible, even if the specimens are as small as 0.16T CTSs. It is, therefore, worth developing an alternative procedure, which can be used when testing sufficient specimens to apply the inhomogeneity analysis outlined in Appendix X5 of [4] is not feasible, or when reanalysing historic data.

One possibility is to utilise the FRACTESUS data in the form illustrated in *Figure 4* to produce “typical” values of the uncertainty on mini- T_0 associated with material inhomogeneity, and incorporate this in the margin adjustment. The average values of $\sigma_{material\ variability}$ in the FRACTESUS RPV steels were 19°C for the

welds and 7°C for the base metals. The results of using these typical values of material variability for 73W and JRQ are shown in Figure 28.

- Figure 28a and b compare the K_{Jc} data for 73W weld with the “5% lower bounds” calculated using $T_0+1\sigma_{total}$ and $T_0+2\sigma_{total}$, based on the 0.16T subsets from VTT and UoB. (These are the subsets producing the lowest and highest T_0 values, respectively, for 73W.) σ_{total} was determined by RSS addition of the σ_{T_0} determined for each subset and the average $\sigma_{material\ inhomogeneity}$ for welds (19°C).
The $T_0+1\sigma_{total}$ margin adjustment derives “5% bounds” from the 0.16T data which range from clearly non-conservative to slightly conservative with respect to the $\geq 1T$ K_{Jc} measurements. The $2\sigma_{total}$ adjustment produces bounds which range from conservative to over-conservative.
- Figure 28c compares the K_{Jc} data from $>0.16T$ samples of JRQ base metal, with the “5% lower bounds” calculated from $T_0+2\sigma_{total}$, based on the 0.16T subsets from HZDR and PSI (the lowest and highest values respectively). Overall, 7% of the $>0.16T$ data lie below the PSI bound and 1% below the HZDR bound; considering only the 1T data, 8% lie below the PSI bound and 2% below the HZDR bound. The $2\sigma_{total}$ adjustment thus produces bounds which range from good to conservative.
- Figure 27b (and Table 8) show that the $2\sigma_{total}$ adjustment for 15Kh2MFAA produces good or conservative bounds from 5 of 6 subsets, but non-conservative bounds (9% of data below the “5% bound”) in the last subset.

Figure 28: Comparisons between data and “5% bounds” associated with T_0 values derived from subsets of 0.16T data with margin adjustments including material inhomogeneity contributions of 19 $^{\circ}C$ for weld and 9 $^{\circ}C$ for base metal
 (a) 73W weld (VTT subset, cum prob=0.19, UoB subset cum prob=0.90) $1\sigma_{total}$ adjustment
 (b) 73W weld $2\sigma_{total}$ adjustment
 (c) JRQ plate $2\sigma_{total}$ adjustments based on T_0 from PSI (cum prob=0.23) and HZDR (cum prob=0.90) subsets.

In summary, using the $2\sigma_{total}$ margin-adjustment with the average values of $\sigma_{material}$ variability will generally produce “5% bounds” which are predominantly (88% of these three datasets) good or conservative descriptions of K_{IC} measurements on $\geq 1T$ samples: in the remaining datasets, the overly-conservative predictions are offset by the non-conservative predictions. **This constitutes the best practice feasible when it is not possible to test 30 or more 0.16T CTSS.**

7 Conclusions and Recommendations

- Examination of toughness data from both large and small specimens within FRACTESUS has shown that the T_0 values measured in different laboratory campaigns on a given material generally vary by more than expected from the value of σ_{T0} proposed in the ASTM Standard E1921-21.
 - This appears to be due to material inhomogeneity and is evident in data from both welds and base metals.
 - Typical values of the uncertainty ascribable to material inhomogeneity in small specimens were found to be around 19°C for welds and 7°C for base metals.
 - Of two materials examined in detail, the uncertainty in $\geq 1T$ specimens was smaller than that in 0.16T specimens; in the other it was not.
- Stakeholders have been concerned that the volume of material in the plastic zone ahead of the crack front in a miniature CTS is too small to be properly representative of a RPV steel. Metallographic observations in the literature coupled with examination of the toughness data acquired from 0.16T CTSs within FRACTESUS show that this concern is justified. Both base metals and welds are likely to contain more than one constituent in islands of diameters of the order fractions of a mm – several mm (e.g. recrystallised and as-deposited regions of a weld bead, islands of ferrite / bainite / martensite reflecting the dendrite spacing of castings). Each constituent will contain a population of weak links and the distributions of strengths in the different populations may or may not overlap.
 - If material inhomogeneity is suspected over long length scales, then specimens should be cut from widely-separated locations so that the extent of the inhomogeneity can be assessed.
- Material inhomogeneity in the RPV steels examined within FRACTESUS occurred over size scales such that the crack front in a 1T (25mm) specimen sampled sufficient material that the population of weak links in the weaker constituent was always represented. Smaller specimens sometimes contained the weaker constituent along the crack front, but not always. If insufficient material from the weaker constituent is present, then the toughness measurement in the small sample will reflect the population of weak links in the less brittle constituent.
 - Within FRACTESUS, the size scales of the inhomogeneities in the materials examined were such that 0.16T and 1T specimens behaved differently.
 - Comparing FRACTESUS 0.16T data with data from pcCvs and CTSs in the literature showed that the change in behaviour did not necessarily occur between 0.16T and larger specimens but could occur between 0.4T (pcCv) or 0.5T and larger specimens, depending on the material.
- When inhomogeneity affected 0.16T specimens but not 1T specimens, then T_0 from the small specimens was lower than that of the large specimens.

- In one case (73W), the difference was such that the T_0 values did not overlap at the 3σ level, when σ was identified as σ_{T_0} .
- In consequence of the size scales of material inhomogeneity, the lower bounds to the distribution of K_{Ic} measurements from $\geq 1T$ samples could not always be predicted from 0.16T data:
 - When the entire FRACTESUS datasets were utilised to define T_0 and σ_{T_0} , the $2\sigma_{T_0}$ margin adjustment procedure did not lead to good or conservative predictions of the lower bounds to the $\geq 1T$ data.
 - Replacing T_0 with T_{0scrn} allowed the full 0.16T datasets to predict the bounds to the $\geq 1T$ data in only two of three steels examined in detail.
 - The bounds derived from the full inhomogeneity analyses, whether bimodal or multimodal, were appropriate or conservative.
- For a given volume of material, the crack front will be longer if the volume is cut into smaller samples. Using smaller samples will then provide a more representative description of the material behaviour. In contrast, if small samples are used to reduce the crack front length tested, then the description may become non-conservative. Examination of the FRACTESUS data suggests that at least 30 0.16T specimens are required to avoid this situation.
- The sizes of the individual subsets of data acquired in the laboratories of the different FRACTESUS partners were more representative of the number of 0.16T specimens likely to be tested in practice, and generally too small to permit a full inhomogeneity analysis.
 - Using T_0 and σ_{T_0} derived from these data subsets, the 2σ margin-adjustment was generally non-conservative in its prediction of the $\geq 1T$ data.
 - Using T_{0scrn} was non-conservative in half the cases.
 - When the magnitude of σ associated with T_0 was increased by the uncertainty associated with material inhomogeneity, then the $2\sigma_{total}$ -margin-adjustment led to the 5% lower bound being a good or conservative description of the $\geq 1T$ data.

$$\sigma_{total}^2 = \sigma_{T_0}^2 + \sigma_{material\ variability}^2$$

On the basis of this investigation, the appropriate treatment of 0.16T data, to make allowance for material inhomogeneity at a scale between 0.16T and 1T requires that:

- Samples be cut from as wide a variety of locations as possible to enhance the likelihood of picking up representative levels of inhomogeneity;

- Sufficient measurements be made that a reliable inhomogeneity analysis can be performed ($N > 20$, according to ASTM, but further statistical analysis of the FRACTESUS data could modify this), and the 5% lower bound be determined from either a bimodal or multimodal analysis.

or, if this is not possible,

- A $2\sigma_{\text{total}}$ margin adjustment be made to T_0 , in which the $\sigma_{\text{material variability}}$ is taken as at least 7°C for a base metal or 19°C for a weld.

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